

Pre-Distribution of Microservices Among Containers in Cloud Environment

Abdul Saboor

High Performance Cloud Computing Center (HPC)
Universiti Teknologi Petronas
Sri Iskandar 32610, Malaysia
abdul_19001745@utp.edu.my

Ahmad Kamil Mahmood

High Performance Cloud Computing Center (HPC)
Universiti Teknologi Petronas
Sri Iskandar 32610, Malaysia
kamilmh@petronas.com.my

Mohd Fadzil Hassan

Institute of Autonomous System for Autonomous Facilities
Universiti Teknologi Petronas
Sri Iskandar 32610, Malaysia
mfadzil_hassan@utp.edu.my

Abstract—Cloud Computing is an ever evolving paradigm. The cloud services widely shifted from monoliths to microservices. Microservices gained the popularity for use in scalable cloud application. The usage of microservices involved intensive network communication to call number of interdependent microservices running inside the cloud/edge nodes.

This study address the pre-distribution strategies of container-based microservices and propose two distribution strategies named as Random Distribution and Design Pattern Distribution. In random distribution approach the microservices are assigned arbitrarily to the available data centers. While in design pattern distribution the microservices are grouped together on the basis of behavioral design patterns which identifies common communication patterns among objects.

The proposed solution was tested using custom built simulation environment. The achieved results showed that the early distribution of microservices according to the design pattern of the application resulted in significant reduction of network calls to the microservices hosted at other network nodes or data centers.

Index Terms—Cloud Computing, Microservices, Container, Optimization, Distribution Strategies

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last decade significance of the data centers has increased dramatically and they are considered as backbone of the modern economy. The cloud application are widely used by startups to big industries. According to American National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) "Cloud Computing is a model which enables ubiquitous, convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g., networks, servers, storage, applications, and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction" [1]. Cloud computing delivers massive opportunities for all enterprises and organizations to have easier running and flexible business models [2]. The cloud computing provides a mechanism through which the processing/computational

power and storage is provided through cloud infrastructure. Few of such cloud service providers include Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, Google Cloud Platform (GCP), Kamatera, and IBM Cloud. The cloud computing gives the advantage of pay-as-you-go model, elasticity, and on demand provisioning of resources [3]. The services models provided by the cloud are mainly categorized into three parts [1] [4] i.e. Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Software as a Service (SaaS). 1) *Software as a Service (SaaS)*: Software as Service is also known as cloud application services. The SaaS provides access to cloud based software. Through web or API, the users access the software residing on remote cloud network. In SaaS, the vendor manages most of the technical issues including data handling, storage, servers etc. Therefore, the users do not have to spend more time on installing, maintaining, and upgrading software. Some of the SaaS examples are Dropbox, Salesforce, GoToMeeting, Google Apps etc. 2) *Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS)*: In IaaS, the cloud computing vendors provides access of resources such as storage, computing resource and networking. IaaS let the businesses to purchase the resources according to their need/demand. Therefore, the IaaS provides a flexible cloud computing model where clients have complete control on infrastructure. As the whole infrastructure is based on cloud so their will be no single point of failure. Some of the IaaS examples are Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, Google Compute Engine (GCE) etc. 3) *Platform as a Service (PaaS)*: PaaS provides a framework for the users (specifically: developers) on which they can develop, manage and deploy the applications. The users not only have access to computing and storage resource, but they also have access to set of tools for application development, testing, security, backups etc. PaaS has number of advantage including scalability, high availability, and cost effective development and deployment platform. Some of the PaaS examples are Apache Stratos,

AWS Elastic Beanstalk, Google App Engine etc.

Cloud computing model provides access to pool of configurable computing resources. The cloud data centers relies on the concept of virtualization to provide access to the shared resources and security [5]. For the last few years there had been a shift towards the containerization. The concept of containers creates lightweight and flexible environment by allowing applications to share operating system. Therefore, containers are form of OS virtualization. Recent advancement in container technology have encouraged organization and researchers to use the containers in the cloud environment. The adoption of containers helped in embarrassment of microservices at cloud level. Microservices offer number of advantages such as scalability, reliability, re-usability, fast response time, reduced cost, and many more [6] [7]. Microservices also comes with number of challenges. The microservices adoption challenges include security vulnerabilities [8] [9], finding the right size and number of services [7].

As microservices are independent units and often needs to interact with other microservices. The large number of microservices and their interaction thus increases the communication overhead. One way to provide reliable and fast communication is by decreasing the communication among physical machine hosted at multiple data centers. This study suggests different ways to distribute the microservices on physical machines so that the microservices have to use lesser communication network. The microservices are ordered/managed in such a way that they mostly interact with the microservices available at same physical machine and do not have to interact most of time with the microservices hosted on other physical machines.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In cloud computing one of the most critical factor is to provide quality of service (QoS) within the defined constraints. Few of the constraints include response time, throughput, minimum service un-availability, low cost, execution or completion time limits. This section outlines some of the existing research studies performed to meet the QOS constraint.

Traditionally, heuristic scheduling algorithms had been used to minimize the processing time and schedule tasks efficiently. A study by Juarez et.al [10] used the polynomial-time algorithm that combines the set of heuristic rules and resource allocation technique to execute task based applications efficiently on distributed computing platforms.

The design shift of cloud services from monolithic applications to loosely coupled micro-services brought in many challenges. The number of micro-services can vary from few micro-services (for a simple application e.g. cinema movie booking platform) to hundreds of micro-services (complex applications e.g. netflix, amazon, twitter etc), refer Fig. 1.

The container placement strategy in a CaaS as proposed by Zhang et al. [12] achieved energy saving by optimization. They did the placement of containers using improved genetic algorithm (IGA). The containers were placed on VMs which were hosted on physical machines (PM). It was considered

Fig. 1. Network of microservices, service-to-service communication of Amazon and Netflix [11]

that VMs can meet resource requirement of all new containers, and only two resources were considered i.e. CPU and memory. According to authors in conventional genetic algorithm (GA) it is hard to get better chromosome (consisting of container ID and VM ID) that fits better when VM resource utilization is high. Therefore, the introduced IGA showed better results in terms of energy saving when compared to spread and bin-packing strategies, first fit and conventional GA. However, the study only considered the energy saving parameter and the parameters like high availability, low resource wastage were not studied. According to authors, the proposed strategies only applies to static placement of container and was unable to support real-time scheduling and relocation. Thus dynamic container consolidation is still an open issue.

Docker containers are used to perform OS level virtualization. According to Zhang [13] container placements on VM is an issue. The VM placement and container placement should not be addressed individually, therefore Zhang proposed a solution named *Container-VM-PM*. The solution resulted in optimization of the placement of new containers and minimized the number of physical machines and resource wastage.

In a study by Lin [14], the container-based microservice scheduling was done based on multi-objective optimization method using an ant colony optimization algorithm. The solution took into account the utilization of computing and memory resources of physical machines and also considered the number of microservice requests and the failure rate of physical nodes. However, the study considered microservice scheduling in single container only, and did not considered the producer consumer relationship of the microservices.

The optimization of service request routing in the microservice system was also addressed by Yz et al. [15] in 2019. According to them the existing solutions are not optimized for chain-oriented services provisioning. Thus the study focused on microservice instance placement and optimization of resource allocation. The proposed schema resulted in near-optimal solution for instance creation, balanced request routing, better load balancing while instance deployment, and reduction in overall energy consumption. However the microservices placement decision was based on post execution of services, and did not addressed the pre-execution distribution

Fig. 2. Random selection and distribution of microservices to the data centers

of microservices.

Lv et al. [16] proposed the container distribution strategies to address the problem of heavy communication workloads among containers. For container placement they proposed the worst fit decreasing algorithm, and for container assignment proposed a two stage Sweep and Search algorithm. The experimental results showed the reduction in communication overhead among the containers.

Srikantaiah [17], is one the earliest researcher who addressed the consolidation to enable energy efficiency for the cloud computing environment. Later on Tchana et al. [18] used virtual machine consolidation and dynamic application sizing strategies together which helped in avoiding holes in resources (i.e. unused resources). The experiments were performed in private cloud using VM on PM, however only Tomcat servlet was hosted using container.

Zhou, Li, and Wu [19] proposed the optimal placement schema for containers in the cloud environment. They introduced one-shot algorithm which work as placement schema for the container cluster, and an online algorithm which breaks down the online decision making into on-spot decision depending on resource price.

Recently another study by Sampaio et. al [20] proposed an adaption mechanism, named as REMaP (Run-time Microservices Placement). In this model the automatic run-time placement of microservices is based upon usage history of resources and microservices affinity.

The literature review showed one common concern that heavy network communication and latency is one of the major issue in container based cloud environment. Especially the decomposition of a particular application into many small microservices results into large round trips between service calls. The possible solution could be aggregating multiple services or batch service call in a single round trip, or replacing expensive inter-process communication call with language-level function calls [21]. This study propose an early distribution of container-based microservices in Cloud/Edge environment such that the microservices are grouped in such a way that it results in lower number of network calls. The solution addressed the distribution of microservices and

containers at early stages of application deployment.

III. METHODOLOGY

The containers are mostly used for the deployment of microservices in cloud and edge computing environment. For this paper the distribution of microservices is considered in such a way that one container hosts one and only one microservice in the cloud/edge environment. This section describes two proposed microservice distribution approaches i.e. Randomized Distribution, and Design Pattern Distribution.

A. Randomized Distribution

The random distribution and assignment approach does not take into account any performance parameters while assigning the containers to randomly chosen physical machine of the data centers. The services are deployed arbitrarily i.e. without any consideration of performance parameters. Therefore this way of assignment can also be termed as a classical approach.

The microservices are assigned randomly and the assigned containers are distributed across random location. Thus resulting in no consideration of design pattern or microservices interaction.

The random distribution approach is shown in Fig.2 where the randomize function selects a microservices on random basis and assign it to the random pools. Then these pools of microservices are randomly assigned to the available data centers.

In such a random distribution there is high chance that a microservice assigned to on data center is totally dependent on a microservice available at other data center. Thus, the execution of such microservices is likely to place multiple network communication calls between services for successful execution.

Fig. 3. Arrangement of microservices according to their interaction dependencies and assignment to the data centers

B. Design Pattern Distribution

The term *pattern* used by software designers describes the software abstraction, thus patterns used across other procedures, subroutines, and objects may also combine for more common abstraction [22]. According to [23] it is set of related patterns which provides the building blocks and these building blocks are built upon the other blocks thus defining the pattern application sequence. For this study we considered the

Fig. 4. Number of microservices calls originated from the system over a period of one hour

Fig. 5. Number of network calls in Random Distribution of microservices

Fig. 6. Number of network calls in Design Pattern Distribution of microservices

Fig. 7. Comparison of Random Distribution (RD) and Design Pattern Distribution (DPD) network calls

behavioral patterns as these design patterns are concerned with communication between objects.

The proposed design pattern distribution schema is shown in Fig.3, where microservices are assigned according to interaction defined in software design. If two or more microservices are dependent on each other for the execution of services, then those microservices are pooled together and assigned to respective containers. Then these pools of container are assigned to the respective data centers.

Contrary to other studies, here we have addressed the distribution of containers before even execution of the services, which can result in better response time and less number of network calls for execution of service request.

C. Results and Discussion

To assess the proposed techniques, we designed the simulation program to produce the microservices utilization data sets. To get the insights of the produced data sets we used an online tool called plotly [24]. Plotly provided online analytic and visualization of the data sets.

The data sets were produced for one hour of microservices calls, and for the assessment of the proposed system it was considered that maximum of 1000 calls can be originated for the microservices at any given time. The atomized simulation process however reached maximum of 729 simultaneous microservices calls at a given time. The number of service calls originated from the system are shown in Fig.4. They are the simulated calls for microservices which will be used for testing the random and design pattern distribution.

To get the test results for classical random approach, the service calls were originated for the microservices distributed

randomly at containers in random location i.e. data centers. The number of network calls placed by the microservices in random distribution are shown in Fig. 5. It clearly shows that heavy network traffic is generated by such a distribution. On average 189 network calls were placed at a given time.

In the second simulation the design pattern distribution strategy was tested and the results showed that the number of network calls reduced significantly. On average 84 network calls we placed at a given time, which are very low when compared to random distribution. The low number of network calls were due to the availability of containers (having required microservice) in close proximity

The comparison of both distribution strategies is shown in Fig. 7 which clearly indicate the better performance of design pattern based distribution over the random distribution of microservices hosted on the containers in cloud environment.

During the multiple simulation run of the system, it was noted that for couple of time the design pattern based distribution of network calls exceeded the random distribution network calls, but it was rare. This was due to the ideal match of the microservices calls and the distribution done during the random distribution. Thus less network calls placed in such a configuration were by coincidence.

D. Conclusion and Future Work

The design shift of cloud services from monolithic applications to loosely coupled micro-services brought in many challenges. This study addressed the communication issues and proposed two microservices distribution strategies to reduce the network calls. The random distribution and design pattern distribution were suggested, and the simulation tests showed

that the early distribution of microservices according to the design pattern of application significantly reduce the network call to other microservices.

The proposed system was tested using a custom built data sets and the system further needs to be tested using real cloud traces. In future the study will also be extended by defining other early distribution strategies such as priority based distribution and weighted mean average distribution.

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